

Article

The Importance of Skills in Career Development

TODERICIU Ramona¹ and GRAMA Blanca^{2,*}

¹ Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania; ramona.todericiu@ulbsibiu.ro; <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-2567-0241>

² Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania; blanca.grama@ulbsibiu.ro; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6209-4776>

* Correspondence: blanca.grama@ulbsibiu.ro

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Abstract: *The purpose of this paper is to investigate how individual career management is related to career sustainability, analyzing the role of skills in career development. The study surveyed 120 employees, collecting data through a structured questionnaire. The findings highlight the essential role of skills in creating and maintaining a competitive advantage in the labor market. This research adds to the growing body of literature by empirically validating the importance of skills in competitive strategy and provides practical implications for managers seeking to leverage these resources for sustained competitive success.*

Keywords: *Skills; Labor Market; Career*

“The best investment in our future is the investment in our people. Skills and education drive Europe’s competitiveness and innovation. But Europe is not yet fully ready. I will ensure that we use all the tools and funds at our disposal to redress this balance.”
President Von der Leyen

1. Introduction

Employees are much more active, engaged and responsible for managing their careers now than they were in the past. The 21st century is called the century of change; change is a constant in the life of modern organizations, supporting organizations to adapt to the transformations of the exogenous environment, adaptation often being a condition of their survival. In this context, we are witnessing a strengthening of the role of human capital in the sustainable development of organizations, an increasing attention paid to approaches based on skills generated by an indisputable truth that skills contribute and will contribute decisively to the increase of competitiveness and performance of organizations modern.

Careers are now increasingly dynamic, characterized by frequent organizational and occupational changes and horizontal and lateral career moves. These changes raise important challenges for all actors involved. A particular challenge involves how to protect career sustainability now that careers are increasingly characterized by unpredictability. A common and important dimension within each career management model is the career goal, defined as any desired career outcome, such as promotion, salary increase, or skill acquisition that individuals wish to achieve (Seibert et al., 2013).

Without a single template to set the standard for a particular career path, the possible career trajectories for employees become virtually limitless. Instead of an organization providing a particular type of structure for career advancement, employees might rely on identification with particular groups to help define and create career goals within the career management process. Identification with a relevant group can replace institutionalized career structures and provide a compass for an individual beyond

the walls of an employing organization. Regarding the achievement of short-term objectives formulated by the employee, professional identification with a group correlates positively with specific, difficult objectives: for the achievement of long-term objectives, psychosocial mentoring is directly related to the quality of the objective (Greco, Kraimer, 2020).

Referring to the career approach from the perspective of the boundless career and the protean career, the responsibility to navigate the career and establish their own career trajectories rests with the employee, not the employer (Arthur & Rousseau, 1996; Eby et al., 2003); which means that the establishment and content of career objectives belong to the employee, who is responsible for the management of his career. These two paradigms argue that because careers no longer unfold within a single organizational setting, individuals are ultimately responsible for their own careers.

A career can be seen as sustainable when it allows people to be and remain happy, healthy and productive over time (De Vos et al., 2020). Career management is a key factor for a sustainable career including managing activities that help develop social networking skills and career opportunities. The career sustainability perspective sees career management as a shared responsibility of both organizations and individuals (Van der Heijden et al., 2020).

The sustainable career paradigm does not deny this individual responsibility for a sustainable career; she argues that organizations also play an important role as they provide work experiences, development opportunities and support for work-life balance and are therefore actively involved in protecting and improving workplace sustainability. As such, this paradigm emphasizes the critical role of both individual and organizational career management in fostering employees' happiness, health, and productivity in their careers over time (Van der Heijden et al., 2020). Career goals provide an organizing standard that guides career decisions by motivating the choices and managing outcomes. At the same time, managing and achieving objectives generates implications on job satisfaction, organizational commitment and work involvement (Allen et al., 2017).

Boundless careers... Are the way of the future and the only question is how we learn to live in a world of boundaries. (Gunz et al., 2000). They note that it would be more appropriate to identify the boundaries that exist in contemporary workplaces and understand the implications of these barriers for different groups of employees.

Several groups of variables have been examined as antecedents of effective career self-management behaviors. DeFillippi and Arthur (1994) describe three "critical competencies" for successful boundaryless career management. Knowing what a career entails, having a well-formed career identity and a clear set of professional values and goals; possessing the necessary knowledge and skills to perform tasks effectively, as well as the ability to develop new skills.

Regarding career self-management, we can also mention proactive personality, defined as a behavioral tendency to implement or change one's environment (Bateman & Crant, 1993). Employees with proactive personality traits are likely to engage in a variety of career self-management behaviors that select, create, and influence work situations to increase the likelihood of career success and contribute to effective career behavior (Fuller & Marler, 2009).

Another major ingredient for successful career self-management is adaptability, defined as an individual's psychosocial resources to cope with current and anticipated career development tasks, occupational transitions, and occupational trauma. Proactive personality and adaptability represent the psychosocial resources that individuals are able to bring to career management (Savickas, 2005; Savickas & Porfeli, 2012). Career construction theory views adaptation to career transitions as promoted by five principle types of behaviors: orientation, exploration, establishment, management, and disengagement. These constructive activities form a cycle of adaptation that repeats itself periodically as new transitions appear on the horizon. As each transition approaches, individuals can adapt more effectively if they meet the change with increasing awareness, information seeking followed by informed decision making, trial behavior leading to a stable commitment designed for a specific period of time, active role management and eventually deceleration and disengagement (Savickas, 2005).

2. What are skills?

Now, perhaps more than ever, there is a growing need at EU level not only to improve and adapt skills to new labor market demands, but also to anticipate and prepare for what lies ahead. Skills are a response to companies' need to remain competitive while ensuring social equity for all. This explains the EU's decision to declare 2023: the European Year of Skills. The labor market is also undergoing extensive change. The Future of Jobs 2023 report (World Economic Forum, 2024), indicates that by 2027, 43% of work tasks will be automated which means that over 60% of workers will need reskilling by 2027 (but only 50% have access) (World Economic Forum, 2024). All this demonstrates the need to develop human capital, the accumulation of new knowledge and the development of new skills in accordance with these changes.

For Council Recommendation on Key Competences for Life-long Learning: skills are defined as the ability and capacity to carry out processes and use the existing knowledge to achieve results (Official Journal of the European Union, 2018). Skills are people's abilities, knowledge and expertise that are needed to carry out specific tasks or activities effectively. People can acquire these skills through formal education, training, and experiences gained in different settings such as work, volunteer opportunities, and personal interests. (World Economic Forum, 2024).

We emphasized in the first part of this article that the labor market is very dynamic and in constant change generated by changes in the environment, which determined a greater emphasis on the skills of human capital, on the need to adapt them to the requirements current of organizations primarily due to their role in the development of organizations and in achieving performance but also due to their contribution to the development of employees' careers. In figure no. 1 we present the types of skills on which the management professionals identified in the sustainable development of organizations focused.

Figure 1. Different types of skills

Source: World Economic Forum, 2024

Together, hard and soft skills are the tools in your workplace toolkit that help human capital and organizations to accomplish their goals. The skills that powered the business yesterday won't ensure success tomorrow. Technological advancements, market disruptions, and shifts in workforce dynamics are reshaping the way we work (World Economic Forum, 2024). As well as the need to improve skills permanently, adapting them to the requirements of the labor market.

A comparative analysis between the Top 10 important skills in the workforce in 2020 compared to 2015, carried out and presented at the World Economic Forum - Future of jobs report in 2020, is illustrated in figure no. 2. We note the maintenance of the first position of Complex problem solving both in 2015 and in 2020, the maintenance of the other skills in the top 10, but in different positions: coordinating with others, people management, creativity, critical thinking, negotiation, service orientation, judgment and decision making and the exit from the top 10 in 2020 of active listening, quality control and their replacement in the top 10 in the year 2020 with emotional intelligence, cognitive flexibility.

Emotional intelligence, which doesn't feature in the top 10 today, will become one of the top skills needed by all (World Economic Forum, 2016). Interesting is the jump made by creativity which from 10th place in 2015 reached 3rd place in 2020, reflecting the importance of this skill in modern organizations. Creativity will become one of the top three skills workers will need. With the avalanche of new products, new technologies and new ways of working, workers are going to have to become more creative in order to benefit from these changes (World Economic Forum, 2024).

In the same way, we identify critical thinking in the second position, confirming the growth of interest in the so-called power skills, extremely valued and sought after by organizations. In recent years, soft skills have evolved into something more complex, combining human factors with technical expertise to form something new: power skills. Power skills are the perfect fusion of traditional soft skills and hard technical skills, creating a powerful mix essential in today's work landscape. These skills make employees more versatile, adaptable and effective problem solvers. According to the PMI "Pulse of the Profession" 2023 survey, 92% of the survey respondents believe that power skills are absolutely essential in the workplace - regardless of region, industry, or years of experience. This idea is backed up by the Future of Job Skills 2023 report, which shows that today's organizations increasingly expect their employees to bring core skills like analytical thinking, creativity, flexibility, motivation, self-awareness, curiosity, a love for lifelong learning, and a strong sense of ethics to the table (World Economic Forum, 2023).

Figure 2. Top 10 skills important the workforce

Source: World Economic Forum - Future of jobs report 2020

Change won't wait for us: business leaders, educators and governments all need to be proactive in upskilling and retraining people so everyone can benefit from the Fourth Industrial Revolution (World Economic Forum, 2016). These changes in the global labor market will require people to have different skills than they do today. This means that by 2025, a major part of the workforce needs to be reskilled. So what skills are in demand in the near future? What will our jobs in 2025 look like? We'll discuss what those future workspace skills are, why they are important and what we can do to prepare for the Reskilling Revolution.

Analyzing figure no. 3 in which 10 Essential Skills for Every Future Proof Organization according to the World Economic Forum are presented, we observe the changes in terms of the skills appreciated and requested on the labor market. Organizations identify four categories of necessary skills: problem solving, self management, working with people and technology use and development, each containing a number of skills. Thus, the first 5 places in the top 10 are problem solving skills, an extended category that contains five of the most important skills of the year 2025, respectively: Analytical thinking and innovation, active learning and learning strategies, complex problem solving, critical thinking and analysis, creativity, originality and initiative. Problem-solving skills are extremely valuable, being key skills that employers look for in prospective employees.

Figure 3. 10 Essential Skills for Every Future Proof

Source: World Economic Forum, 2024

The second category of skills is represented by self-management and includes active learning and learning strategies and resilience, stress tolerance and flexibility. Self-management is considered by specialists as a category that contains the skill of resilience, stress tolerance, and flexibility, as these are the skills needed to continue to maintain a positive mind even when 'things get tough or when we are faced with unexpected situations. Or it can be defined as the ability to regulate your behaviors, thoughts and emotions in a productive way and excel in both personal and professional responsibilities for the benefit of you and your team (World Economic Forum, 2024). The globalization is a powerful process that generates connection and collaboration between organizations and people, and *to successfully do this, soft skills like empathy, conflict resolution, communication, and decision-making are vital* (World Economic Forum, 2024).

Technology use and development, we expected to be at the top of the skills list given the importance of technology, AI, digitization in our lives and organizations. These skills remain in the top 10 skills for 2025, even if they are not at the top of the list, because they will definitely play a huge role in the future of any industry. Technology has played a major part in our lives for many years now, and this will only continue to grow at an even faster pace by 2025 (World Economic Forum, 2024).

The set of skills analyzed is considered very important for the organizations of the future, having been proven that the lack of the necessary skills is disastrous for organizations because it prevents them from quickly adapting to changes in the exogenous environment, sensing opportunities and capitalizing on

them, improving their performance. It is important for the management of organizations to understand how these future skills add value to the organization and that the involvement and collaboration of all stakeholders are needed to develop these future skills. Part of the solution and what will make the difference is lifelong learning that must become a reality for everyone.

We would all like to know how the labor market will be in 2030. But at this moment, taking into account the complexity and dynamics of the external environment of organizations, it is very difficult to answer this question. Obviously, no one can anticipate what will happen, but we have some interesting predictions: According to Dell, 85% of us who are at work will be doing jobs that don't exist yet (World Economic Forum, 2024). Which means that the labor market will be in continuous change and will definitely require new skills, a combination of technical skills, such as digital literacy and data skills, as well as soft skills, such as emotional intelligence and creativity (World Economic Forum, 2024). In order to be competitive in such a market, an adaptation and development of new essential skills for the new jobs are needed, necessary to face the changes and remain competitive in the labor market, even more so as much as it has been proven that: the skills that powered the business yesterday won't ensure success tomorrow (World Economic Forum, 2024).

3. Methodology

Closing skills gaps and training employees with the right skills for jobs are essential features for creating resilient and productive labor markets. Identifying the right skills will help employers expand their talent pools by hiring for what you know and drive greater productivity and prosperity. For policy makers, a skills-based approach can promote economic prosperity and serve as an asset for local communities. And for the employee, the identification of appropriate skills in the workplace can contribute to the identification and appropriate professional development.

The research question was whether the skills possessed by young employees contributed both to employment and to their professional development. Identifying the right skills as a foundation for career development can help hold both employees and employers accountable for success. With the skills clearly defined for each role, employees will be able to understand their gaps and strengths and be motivated to improve accordingly.

With the objective of identifying employees with the necessary skills in the labor market, we proposed to be conducted a pilot study with as subjects the students from the master's field who are employed. The structured questionnaire method was applied. Using Google Docs, we created a form which virtually represents the online survey. After creating the form, we have sent it directly to people knowing that they work. The structured questionnaire includes a part of General Information and a part that specifically refers to Indicators of career and skills. The measuring instrument (questionnaire) for this research consisted of 12 questions in total that the respondents were asked to answer and express their agreement/disagreement with the proposed statements, whereby the Likert measurement scale of five degrees was used (1=totally disagree; 2=disagree; 3=neither agree nor disagree; 4=agree; 5=total agreement). We mention that all the respondents are graduates of undergraduate studies in different fields.

4. Results and discussions

The questionnaire was sent to 120 respondents through the Google Forms, with a response rate of 81%. 82.8% of respondents work in a private organization, 71.5% hold an executive position, and 41% have less than 5 years of experience in the organization they belong to. 70% of the respondents identified professional development, 14% professional recognition as the essential characteristics to make a career (figure 4).

1. Ce înseamnă pentru dumneavoastră a face carieră. Alegeți o singură variantă de răspuns.

96 de răspunsuri

Figure 4. What it means to make a career

The establishment and content of career goals belong to the employee, who is responsible for the management of his career. The sustainable career paradigm does not deny individual responsibility for a sustainable career; she argues that organizations also play an important role as they provide work experiences, development opportunities and support for work-life balance and are therefore actively involved in protecting and improving workplace sustainability. The respondents identified (figure 5) in a proportion of over 80% the role of the employee in career development, also positioning the role of the organization in the career (55% to a large extent; 28% to a very large extent)

2. Considerați că dezvoltarea carierei dumneavoastră depinde de:

Figure 5. Career development depends on the organization or employee

Professional development and professional recognition were highly valued and to a very large extent to the detriment of professional achievements (to a very small extent). The report is also in agreement with the young age of the respondents who identify more with a professional development than a family one. More than 80% of the respondents belong to the demographic cohort of generation Z, who were formed in a safer, more prosperous world and this made them freer and bolder, more irreverent, more willing to risk and change, more independent. Skills have a major role in the career development of an employee but also in the harmonious and balanced development of organizations. Skills are a response to companies' need to remain competitive while ensuring social equity for all.

Respondents identified curiosity and openness to learning, motivation, communication skills and the ability to work in a team as skills that contributed to employment (figure 6).

4. În ce măsură considerați că următoarele abilități au contribuit la angajarea dumneavoastră:

Figure 6. Skills that contributed to employment

Figure 7 illustrates the extent to which skills such as openness to learning, motivation, confidence in one's own abilities, problem solving and control of the quality of the work performed will contribute to development in the workplace.

5. În ce măsură considerați că următoarele abilități vor contribui la dezvoltarea dumneavoastră la locul de muncă:

Figure 7. Skills that will contribute to developing

The respondents identified in significant proportions openness to learning, motivation, self-confidence, creative thinking as basic skills for development at the workplace. The avalanche of new products, new technologies and new ways of working, workers are going to have to become more creative in order to benefit from these changes. In recent years, soft skills have evolved into something more complex, combining human factors with technical expertise to form something new: self management. Self management is the perfect fusion of traditional soft skills and hard technical skills, creating a powerful mix essential in today's work landscape. These having a significant impact on the control of the quality of work and implicitly on learning. Confidence in one's own abilities is characteristic of young people, those young people of Generation Z who represented a wide range of respondents in the study. These skills make employees more versatile, adaptable and effective problem solvers.

6. În ce măsură considerați că următoarele abilități vor fi importante pentru organizații, indiferent de schimbările ce vor avea loc în viitor în mediul exogen al acestora:

Figure 8. Important skills for organizations in the future

Figure 8 illustrates the important skills for organizations in the future respondents identifying the role of digital skills, problem solving, adaptability and flexibility.

According to PMI, Pulse of the Profession 2023 survey, 92% of the survey respondents believe that power skills are absolutely essential in the workplace – regardless of region, industry, or years of experience. This idea is backed up by the Future of Jobs Report 2024 report, which shows that today's organizations increasingly expect their employees to bring core skills like analytical thinking, creativity, flexibility, motivation, self-awareness, curiosity, a love for lifelong learning, and a strong sense of ethics to the table. The identification of digital skills as the basis for the development of organizations is not surprising because we are in the era of digitalization that floods our lives and organizations. Without digital literacy, managers may struggle to understand and adopt emerging technologies, leading to missed opportunities to increase service value.

5. Conclusion

Future organizations are defined as new organizational forms designed for adaptability and agility, moving from hierarchical structures to virtual team work models and online labor markets. In the context of the future of work, the skills a person has are crucial knowledge for performing tasks more than ever (Chalutz Ben-Gal, 2020). Human capital is certainly the most important intangible asset of organizations and the investment in this asset, for the accumulation of new knowledge and the development of new skills, is an investment in the development of the organization. The set of skills analyzed is considered important for the organizations of the future, having been proven that the lack of the necessary skills is disastrous for organizations because it prevents them from quickly adapting to changes in the exogenous environment, sensing opportunities and capitalizing on them, improving their performance. The lack of opportunities determines, in many cases, the departure of talents from organizations that no longer see career development possibilities, which today, when the struggle to attract talents to organizations is fierce, can generate big problems for organizations through the skills gap that is created, affecting their performance, sometimes even survival. Skills and talent shortages are critical challenges facing societies and economies today. Absence of relevant skills prevent business growth, prevent economic prosperity and employees cannot develop to their maximum potential. Dynamics of the labor market in the future will demand increasingly complex and varied skills, where adaptability and individual flexibility will be indispensable. Moreover, identifying the appropriate skills will contribute to overcoming individual and business success and will contribute to social cohesion. Complementarity between individual skills and organizational requirements will be the basis of employment decisions; a skills-based recruitment process can contribute to the continuous training of employees by offering opportunities for internal mobility.

In summary, our research has highlighted the importance of identifying the right skill sets in a competitive job market. The research revealed the fact that employees leave with a baggage of employment skills that are later adapted to the organization's requirements. The results of this study align with previous research that emphasized the dynamics of skills development and training (World Economic Forum, 2024, 2023; Chalutz Ben-Gal, 2020). It is essential to acknowledge that this study has certain limitations. The generalizability of the results may be limited due to the very small sample size. In addition, this study proposed to be only a pilot study, following which we will carry out a larger research, in which we will also evaluate the opinion of the organizations and analyze the role of educational training in the development of skills that are as competitive as possible on the labor market.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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